

The close connection between spatial stellar distribution and dense interstellar structures in star forming regions

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Abstract

Spatial distribution of young stellar objects (YSOs) in star forming regions (SFRs) may be used as key tracers of their birth sites and their dynamical evolution. Focusing on early stages of star formation, YSOs spatial distribution is expected to follow the dense distribution of gas, and thus be characterised by a strong and clumpy stellar clustering.

We have developed a framework based on DBSCAN algorithm to identify significant overdense spatial stellar substructures at small scales (the NESTs, for Nested Elementary Stellar sStructures). We first apply this methodology to Taurus and identify 20 NESTs mainly distributed along the gaseous filaments, spanning the 5-80kAU size range. We further assess the reliability of our method and applying it to almost 40 star forming regions (SFRs) uncovering more than 250 NESTs. The geometrical and physical properties of the NESTs in quiescent SFRs, such as in Taurus, suggest that these overdense stellar spatial structures may be seen as the discrete modes and pristine signatures of star formation process. As a particular result, obtained in Taurus and more generally in almost 40 SFRs, we identify two trends in the "Number of stars-Size" NEST relation with a threshold around 10-15kAU as a turning point. We suggest that this two trends may be related to different fragmentation regimes of their molecular clump progenitors.

To investigate the hypothesis that connects the cloud fragmentation to clumps of stars, we develop a multi-scale analysis based on a graph-theoretic representation of the hierarchical connection between massive dense cores (MDCs) extracted at different spatial resolution and the Class 0/I YSOs. We present preliminary results obtained for NGC 2264 SFR using the five bands Herschel emission maps covering the region. They highlight the connection between massive dense cores (MDCs) hierarchical fragmentation and the formation of local stellar groups, such as the NESTs.

1 Introduction

Star formation mainly occurs in giant molecular clouds (GMCs) with size up to tens of parsecs (Heyer & Dame, 2015) to form embedded star clusters (Lada & Lada, 2003). GMCs fragment into hierarchical gas components (Houllahan & Scalo, 1992; Rosolowsky *et al.*, 2008) nested within each other, leaving a variety of structures of one level into the next, e.g. ubiquitous filaments, clumps and the most dense cores (André *et al.*, 2014). The latter are the loci in where most of the stars form during the last fragmentation steps, mainly as multiple systems (Goodwin *et al.*, 2007; Larson, 2003; Duchêne & Kraus, 2013). Pristine spatial distribution of YSOs must then be closely related to the denser parts of the gas distribution.

And indeed, it is now well established that there is a strong correlation between YSOs and gas surface densities in SFRs (Evans *et al.*, 2009; Gutermuth *et al.*, 2011; Kennicutt & Evans, 2012; Vutisalchavakul *et al.*, 2016; Pokhrel *et al.*, 2020). Early studies of close-by SFRs through the study either of stellar groups (Gomez *et al.*, 1993; Gutermuth *et al.*, 2009; Kuhn *et al.*, 2014) or of the two-point correlation function (e.g., Gomez *et al.*, 1993; Kraus & Hillenbrand, 2008; Gutermuth *et al.*, 2009), raise the question whether spatial stellar patterns is directly inherited from the natal gas structure from which they form (Allen *et al.*, 2007), at least before any further dynamical evolution that affects those pristine spatial imprints as shown by Nbody simulations (Goodwin & Whitworth, 2004; Allison *et al.*, 2010).

Figure 1: Taurus molecular cloud. Planck polarized dust map, overlaid by all colors Herschel mosaic maps. YSOs (Espelin & Luhman, 2019) in green marks. This plot has made use of ESASky 3.7 tool, ESAC, Madrid, Spain).

Figure 2: 2MASS extinction map (Juvella & Montillaud, 2016) overlaid by the ellipsoid hull of the NESTs in red (see Joncour *et al.*, 2018). The NESTs were identified using DBSCAN and the procedure we developed that sets the two free parameters of the algorithm to the following values: $\epsilon = 0.11^\circ$ (the radius around a star) and $N_{min} = 4$ (the minimum number of stars within that radius). Black (resp. white) marks are YSOs inside (resp. outside) the NESTs. The NESTs distribution mainly follow the 3 main dense gas filaments of Taurus.

Thus we expect to find very localized stellar pattern, generated on the final steps of fragmentation process that turn the densest parts of molecular gas into YSOs. In order to identify them, we have set-up a robust clustering method to be applied to the spatial stellar distribution. From the detection of significant local spatial fluctuations above random expectation, the clustering algorithm was able indeed to identify these localized overdense pattern of YSOs in groups, e.g. the NESTs (Joncour *et al.*, 2018; González *et al.*, 2021). In order to study more closely their links to the gas fragments, we have developed a graph-theoretic representation of the multi-scale structure of the cloud using Herschel emission maps, to probe to which extent the star properties, such as clustering & multiplicity of YSOs, may be directly inherited from the gas (see Thomasson *et al.*, this conference). Our work intend thus to provide constraints both on the cloud fragmentation process and on star formation scenarios.

In the following, we present, in section 2, the NESTs detection procedure we applied in Taurus and in 39 SFRs (see Gonzalez *et al.*, this conference), then in section 3, the graph-theoretic approach we developed to characterise the fragmentation process of gas in NGC 2264 and study the link of the gas components with the youngest YSOs (Class 0/I objects), and we come to our main conclusions in section 4.

2 NESTs: local dense stellar substructures

2.1 Stellar substructures detection

In order to extract the stellar groups in SFRs, different methods have been applied so far. Gomez *et al.* (1993, Option A) applied a smoothing Gaussian kernel function on the spatial stellar distribution and visually identified individual stellar groups as the independent iso-stellar density contours. Gutermuth *et al.* (2009, Option B) took advantage of the discrete nature of the spatial stellar distribution and used the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) graph-theoretic representation to distribute the stars in disconnected groups (i.e., sub-graphs). This procedure requires (1) to choose an empirical upper branches length threshold beyond which the branches are removed from the MST graph and (2) to discard stellar groups below an ad-hoc minimum number of stars. Then, Kuhn *et al.* (2014, Option C) looked for parametric surface density model associated to individual cluster, and adapt an ellipsoid shape type cluster from the virial sphere model of Hernquist type (Hernquist, 1990; Evans & An, 2005). To derive the free parameters of each cluster, they use the Expectation/Maximization (EM) components mixture optimisation procedure and the Akaike information criterion (AIC) as the estimator of prediction error, to set the number of clusters to be found in each SFR.

All these previously discussed clustering techniques are not able to identify small significant stellar subgroups, either because they are designed to detect structures at larger scale (Option A) or because structures with low YSOs content were directly discarded as Poisson noise (Option B). The smoothing parameter chosen ($0.3''$) chosen for option A applied in Taurus, erases indeed all structures below ~ 150 kAU. The MST procedure (Option B) uses the largest inflexion point of the branch length cumulative distribution (i.e. where the second derivative probability density function (PDF) of the branches length crosses zero), to set the upper threshold length at which the graph will be disconnected. For normal PDF, this inflexion point is located at one standard deviation above the mean, i.e. at the 89% quantile. Thus, it also leads to identify the large structures and, moreover, structures that contains less than an ad-hoc given number of members (usually 10-20) are directly discarded. And finally, Option C imposes the shape and the number of clusters they look for, the shape being associated with a virial equilibrium state that should not yet be achieved for pristine substructures.

After performing a review on clustering techniques (Joncour *et al.*, 2020), we identify the DBSCAN (density based spatial clustering of applications with noise, Ester *et al.* (1996)) algorithm as the suited choice for our purpose. DBSCAN is a non-parametric algorithm; it handles noise and outliers detection and performs a partial clustering. It is able to detect arbitrary shape of clusters, using local connectivity rules to group points together from user requested local neighborhood density condition.

We use the nearest neighbor statistics and the one point correlation function (i.e. first order correlation function) to set the two DBSCAN free parameters (i.e., ϵ , the radius around a star and N_{min} , the minimum number of stars within that radius) such that we are able to extract from the spatial distribution of stars, significant stellar structures with a high significance level above Poisson random expectations (Joncour *et al.*, 2017, 2018; González *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 3: Fraction of Class I (Black), II (Red) and, III (Green) objects within each NEST. From right to left, the NESTs are ordered by decreasing fraction of Class I (or Class II if there is no Class I object), which could correspond to an evolutionary sequence from the younger to the older (Figure reproduced from Joncour *et al.*, 2018).

2.2 Taurus

We first analyze the spatial distribution of the YSOs in Taurus (Fig. 1), one of the most quiescent and nearest SFRs, located at an average distance of ~ 140 pc. Taurus as a whole complex seems to span a distance range between 130pc and 161pc, depending on the selected subcloud of the complex (Torres *et al.*, 2009; Galli *et al.*, 2019). It is worthwhile to note that despite this discrepancy at the scale of the whole region, the very localized NESTs are within a same subcloud, sharing thus a same distance. We apply our procedure, and extract 20 elongated dense «mini-clusters» that we named NESTs, spanning the 5-80kAU size range (Fig. 5). They are distributed along the gas filaments (Fig. 2). They contain in total nearly half the stars of the region, and 75% of the youngest class 0/I YSOs, suggesting strongly thus, that they are the preferred sites of star formation. These NESTs appear to be a substructure level of the loose intermediate groups identified so far in Taurus (Gomez *et al.*, 1993; Kirk *et al.*, 2013) and call for a multi-scale analysis to gain access to the full hierarchical view of the SFR (Joncour *et al.*, 2019, 2021).

Our study also suggests a temporal evolutionary pattern for the formation of these NESTs, since these most probably prolate structures (Joncour *et al.*, 2018) contain a mixed Class population of YSOs (Fig. 3). This shows that newly formed (Class 0/I) YSOs can be found next to other more evolved (Class III) stars. The star formation may then be seen as a continuous process in time, operating in those very localized spatial regions but only over a certain period of time, since as soon as the Class III YSOs reach at most 30% of the NEST

Figure 4: Mean fraction (N_{Class}/N) of Class III (resp. Class II, Class 0/I) YSOs in each size bin of NESTs, color code Green (resp., Red, Black, data from Joncour *et al.*, 2018 paper). N is the total number of YSOs in the NESTs per size bin. Percentage errorbars (Y axis) are estimated from error propagation using Poisson noise counting. No displayed errorbar means there is only one Class member.

population, there is no more Class 0/I YSO. In a speculative way, a renewal of the gas reservoir could take place within the very same gas clump fed by accretion flows during few million years before reaching exhaustion of gas material that would stop locally star formation.

Besides, we highlight two regimes in the (N_* - R) relation of the NESTs (Fig. 5) when plotting the Number of YSOs (N_*) within NESTs as a function of their size R (estimated as the mean radius of their convex hull, $R = \sqrt{A/\pi}$, where A is the area of the convex hull of a NESTs). Using the properties of NESTs found in Taurus from Joncour *et al.* (2018) and in the 39 SFRs sample (Gonzales *et al.* in prep), we identify an increasing linear and scale-free trend beyond ~ 10 -15kAU. Using a minimum least square fit for the NESTs size above 13kAU, we obtain:

$$N_* \propto R^\alpha \quad (1)$$

with $\alpha = 0.92 \pm 0.18$ (Taurus) and $\alpha = 1.35 \pm 0.11$ (39 SFRs). Since, for a uniform stellar density distribution we would expect an exponent of 2, the fact that it is much smaller indicates that the bigger NESTs may result from a clustering of small NESTs that add up their YSOs population in a fractal way. This would point to a hidden stellar substructure at lower scale that we would miss in this one-local neighborhood scale analysis but that would be recovered in a multi-scale study.

This increasing linear scale free behavior appears to break for the smaller NESTs below ~ 13 kAU, since based on the extrapolation of the scale free trend found above, we would not expect to find small NESTs harbouring more than 2-3 stars in

the 10-20kAU range, and none structures below 10kAU.

We check whether we may highlight a dynamical expansion signature in the scale free regime of the (N_*, R) relation. Under dynamical expansion, we would expect a larger fraction of class III (resp. 0/I) objects in bigger (resp. smaller) NESTs. If we may notice a potential decrease of Class 0/I objects with the size of the NESTs, we do not see a clear increase of the Class III YSOs (Fig. ??). At this stage, it is then difficult to conclude on a signature of a potential dynamical status of the NESTs, we make thus the hypothesis that the (N_*, R) relation may highlight two pristine modes of stellar groups. The small (resp. big) NESTs would come from fragmentation and collapse of a single (resp. cluster of) gas clump(s). It may then highlight two regimes of cloud fragmentation process: a fractal one down to $\sim 10 - 15$ kAU threshold below which the number of YSOs in stellar groups (NESTs) supersede the one expected from the fractal trend seen at larger scale.

2.3 NESTs catalog from 39 SFRs analysis

Our stellar clustering procedure combining DBSCAN on one hand, and one point correlation function and nearest neighbor statistics on the other hand, has been improved, calibrated with the extensively tested s2d2 tool (González *et al.*, 2021). Then it has been applied (Gonzalez *et al* this conference) to MYStIX (Feigelson *et al.*, 2013) and SFINCs (Getman *et al.*, 2017) SFRs catalogs, to retrieve 254 NESTs from the 39 combined regions (Gonzalez *et al* in prep). First results dedicated to the (N_*, R) NEST relation in 39 SFRs highlight similar trends as observed in Taurus (Fig. 5). This suggests a comparable gas fragmentation processes in the (5-100kAU) range scale, even if this SFRs sample includes very different kind of physical environment, from massive SFRs to intermediate and low mass SFRs.

A first key empirical observation to ground our understanding of star formation process from molecular cloud, is the established power-law relation between surface densities of gas and young stars (Gutermuth *et al.*, 2011; Lada *et al.*, 2013; Willis *et al.*, 2015). It extends the Kennicutt-Schmidt power-law relation type obtained at extra-galactic scales (Kennicutt, 1998) down to galactic molecular clouds (Pokhrel *et al.*, 2020). It also allows to establish the alternative form of the Kennicutt-Schmidt's law stating that the star formation rate scales as a power-law with the gas density, leading to the conclusion that star formation efficiency is very small (Kennicutt, 1998; Pokhrel *et al.*, 2020).

To investigate this star-gas connection in a different way, Gonzalez *et al.* (this conference) applied the MST procedure (Gutermuth *et al.*, 2009) to the spatial distribution of NESTs in each SFR of the MYStIX and SFINCs catalogs to find the spatial concentration of NESTs and compare them with the underlying molecular gas surface density. She found indeed that this correlation between high stellar densities and the gas stands for a set of SFRs, e.g. NGC2264, but does not always apply, e.g. NGC6611 (alternative names: M16 and Eagle), as shown on Figure 6.

In our analysis the strong concentration of stellar NESTs is a sign of youth, and indeed those two SFRs, resp. NGC 6611 and NGC 2264, are very young, based on their isochronal estimated ages, resp. 2Myr (Bell *et al.*, 2013) and 3Myr (Dahm, 2008) or even younger (Venuti *et al.*, 2019) as derived from isochronal studies. But looking at the dense gas distribution as shown by $500\mu\text{m}$ Herschel emission maps (Fig. 6), NGC 6611 appears to be much more evolved than NGC2264

Figure 5: Number of YSOs in NESTs as a function of their size in log-log plot (red mark). The linear increase part of the (N_*, R) relation for the NESTs above 13kAU (beyond the vertical dashed light blue line) in the log-log plot has been fitted by: $N_* \propto R^\alpha$ (linear light blue line). The horizontal dashed dark blue line indicates the mean number of YSOs for NESTs having a size below 13kAU. **Top** NESTs in Taurus, $\alpha = 0.92 \pm 0.18$ (data from Joncour *et al.* (2018)). **Bottom** NESTs data collected from the 39 SFRs. The fit has been done the values evaluated per bins, $\alpha = 1.35 \pm 0.11$ (Gonzalez *et al* in prep).

Figure 6: Grayscale Herschel $500\mu\text{m}$ emission map of NGC 6611 (Top, alternate names M16, Eagle) and NGC 2264 (Bottom) SFRs with the 99.5 percentile emission level contour shown in red. Intensity maps are overlaid by convex hull of NESTs concentrations (in blue) and by OB stars (in green).

as no dense gas coincides any longer with the NESTs concentration and is observed rather as dispersed clumpy gas remnants. This probably reflects the impact of the large number of massive OB stars within the NGC 6611 region, that triggers rapid gas dispersal within less than 3Myr, whereas dense gas is still present in NGC 2264 and undergoes active gas fragmentation to give birth to a large number of YSOs siblings.

3 multi-scale fragmentation of cloud

As seen in the previous section, since there is still this great connection between gas and YSOs surface densities, NGC 2264 appears to be the perfect SFR to investigate in great detail how fragmentation turns gas into stars.

Located at 720pc (Cantat-Gaudin *et al.*, 2018), NGC 2264 is an intermediate-mass SFR, displaying a star forming history from North to South and a current active star formation episodes in two central hubs (Nony *et al.*, 2021). NGC 2264 was observed at millimeter wavelength as part of the Herschel HOBYS project (Motte *et al.*, 2010) and at Spitzer infrared wavelength (Rapson *et al.*, 2014). From those IR observations, 87 class 0/I YSOs have been identified mainly located in the two main central gas clouds (Fig. 7).

Thomasson *et al.* (this conference and in prep) develops a data processing flow applied individually on the five 70-500 μm Herschel maps (giving access to 8"-36" spatial resolution range). Using getsf, the multi-scale and multi-wavelength algorithm to extract dense gas structures from complex background (Men'shchikov, 2021), 414 massive gas clumps (MDCs) were identified with length scales ranging

Figure 7: NGC 2264 SFR. In the background, laid the Planck polarized dust map, overlaid by $500\mu\text{m}$ Herschel map. Class 0/I YSOs (Rapson *et al.*, 2014) are in green marks. This plot has made use of ESASky 3.7 tool, ESAC, Madrid, Spain.

from 6 to 26kAU.

A new graph-theoretic approach has been proposed to study how these MDCs connect from one scale to the others building an oriented network, where the nodes are either the MDCs or the YSOs, and the oriented links are established as inclusive relation between two nodes (i.e. an oriented link connects any one node to a second one, if the latter is included in the former, Fig. 8). This method using independently the 5 emission maps is an alternative to the hierarchical dendrogram (tree) representation (Houlahan & Scalo, 1992; Rosolowsky *et al.*, 2008) built from the intrinsically nested iso-density contours of one column density map that unfortunately loses the best spatial resolution performance that the Herschel intensity maps offer (Thomasson *et al.* in prep).

From this graph-theoretic representation, 3 different types of fragmentation structure have been identified as disconnected subnetworks that we designated as hierarchical, linear and isolated structures (Fig. 9).

Hierarchical structures are mainly located in the central parts of the SFRs and are highly YSOs productive, since an average of 3.4 Class 0/I YSOs are observed per hierarchical structure. Thus, the final fragmentation steps of the gas could indeed induce both the small (resp. bigger) NESTs formation, as the imprints of one hierarchical fragmentation structure (resp. of few hierarchical fragmentation structures close from each other).

In linear structures only an average of 0.2 Class 0/I are observed; star formation appears to be less effective in here while isolated gas structures are by definition infertile, at

Figure 8: Graph-theoretic scheme of the fragmentation network. The oriented network is composed by Class 0/I YSOs and cores as nodes. The oriented links are established as inclusive relation between two nodes (i.e. an oriented link connects any one node to one other if the latter is included in the former).

least for the time being.

We note also that within some gas fragments both smaller gas component and Class 0/I YSO may coexist, confirming that star formation may occur within a same gas clump but at a different time (delayed fragmentation). This study explores a gas clumps scale range similar to the NESTs size range, and reveals a fractal fragmentation close to be binary (1.4). This latter relation remains to be compared in more depth to the fractal trend (exponent 1.2) observed in the NEST (N_*-R) relation.

Half the MDCs are contained in linear fragmentation structures and almost as many (40%) in hierarchical fragmentation structures. Isolated fragmentation structures represent only 10% of the fragmentation structure population. Based on this analysis, monolithic collapse scenario for star formation (Shu *et al.*, 1987; McKee & Tan, 2003; Krumholz *et al.*, 2009), as well as hierarchical fragmentation scenario, operating (resp. or not) in a global collapse cloud (Vázquez-Semadeni *et al.*, 2019; Krause *et al.*, 2020) (resp., Elmegreen, 2002; Kruijssen, 2012; Krumholz *et al.*, 2019; Krumholz & McKee, 2020), seem to occur equally at the same time in the same complex. Depending of the gas density level, monolithic scenario seems to take place on the periphery of the central gas hubs, while the central and densest gas region is more associated with hierarchical fragmentation.

4 Conclusion

The study of the locally very dense stellar structures in SFRs, that we named NESTs provides a great opportunity to identify discrete modes of star formation as the pristine signatures of the last steps of the star formation process that turn gas into stars through fragmentation and gravitational collapse. We began the study with the quiescent Taurus that contains 20 of these NESTs (Joncour *et al.*, 2018), that exhibit an evolutionary pattern that is apparently not due to a dynamical evolution but rather to a potential replenishment of a clump reservoir that may continue to fragment to form YSOs at the same place over an extended period of time. We now retrieve a population of 240 NESTs in 39 other SFRs (Gonzalez *et al.* this conference and in prep). In this latter study, we show that the break of the correlation in a sample of very young SFRs between the highest gas surface density and densest stellar surface density (as identified by the NESTs concentration) is due to the presence of high-mass OB stars, that may disperse the natal gas very quickly in ~ 3 Myr.

Figure 9: 3 types of fragmentation structures highlighted by our work illustrated (Left) as spatial representation of nested gas clumps and (Right) as hierarchical graph-theoretic skeleton (see Thomasson *et al.* this conference). The Massive dense clumps are nearly equally distributed in the two main structures, hierarchical and linear.

In case of very rarefied presence of OB stars, such as in the NGC 2264 SFR, the gas correlates very well with the NESTs concentration, allowing a strong still-ongoing star formation activity. Combining the Herschel emission maps of the gas cloud and the catalog of Class 0/I YSOs, we developed a graph-theoretic representation of the gas fragmentation in NGC 2264 on the 6-30kAU scale (Thomasson *et al.* this conference and in prep). We derived a 1.4 exponent fractal trend between the Number of nodes (MDCs and YSOs) and their scales. Furthermore, we identify two main fragmentation structure types, hierarchical and linear types. They appear to shelter nearly the same amount of MDCs, but are not obviously as efficient to produce YSOs by an order of magnitude (3.4 YSOs per hierarchical structure against 0.2 YSOs per linear structure). We intend to apply this framework to a sample of SFRs and develop a combined multi-scale study between the YSOs distribution and the gas to assess whether the multi-scale structure of the YSOs is indeed directly inherited from the natal gas.

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